

THE IMPACT OF CUSTOMER SERVICE QUALITY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IN ISLAMIC BANKING

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Abstract

The study examines the impact of customer service quality on customer satisfaction in Islamic Banking Industry. In a huge competitive market where rapidly increasing creativity is on peak and customers are provided customized and personalize products by determining their needs and convenience in banking sector of Pakistan. Customer satisfaction plays a catalyst role for any service provider to form consumer's future purchase intentions. Customer service is the managerial procedure which businesses needs to adapt to attract business opportunities, enhance revenue of the business, make more and more reliable access of the market and enhance satisfaction level of customers.

The Islamic banking practices emanates from Islamic laws and thus contrasts in essence, cultural background and practices of conventional banks. Due to intense competition, expectation of customers are very high, Islamic institutions must therefore consider skilfully for providing perceived quality on products and services to satisfy their customers.

INTRODUCTION

Overview of the Study

This current era comprising competitive pressures; most of the financial institutions are meeting their efforts to maintain a loyal customer base. Customer satisfaction is well defined as post purchase evaluation of services and goods. The common aspect of customer satisfaction is the comparison between post and pre purchase assessment of the service experience. It can result from both dimensions whether it is related to quality or not related to quality. Its evaluation may begin from non-quality issues as well and need experience with the service provider.

In a huge competitive market where rapidly increasing creativity is on peak and customers are provided customized and personalize products by determining their needs and convenience in banking sector of Pakistan. Customer satisfaction plays a

catalyst role for any service provider to form consumer's future purchase intentions. Customer service is the managerial procedure which businesses needs to adapt to attract business opportunities, enhance revenue of the business, make more and more reliable access of the market and enhance satisfaction level of customers (Jahanshahi, 2011). A positive connection is also made by elevated levels of service quality and financial performance. The importance of perceived quality is stated by Peeler (1996) that it is a key issue in the banking sector. Customer satisfaction or dissatisfaction is the resultant of Perceived quality of customer services (Jahanshahi, 2011).

The major outcome of marketing activities in Islamic banks is Customer satisfaction. Satisfied customers of bank can create positive word of mouth marketing by telling their encouraging experience to others.

This constructive word of mouth marketing is principally functional in different cultures similar to Pakistan because social relationships and lives are structured in a way to get better in the society. On the other hand, non-satisfied customers of the banks are more likely towards the approach to change banks & having in destructive marketing by word of mouth. Islamic & non-Islamic banking effort together to accomplish bank needs of customers and the core segregation between them is their basis of operations. The basis of operations conducting by Islamic Banking is on the basis of Sharia'h and Laws of Islam (Sowailim, 2013).

Warde (2000) Keeping in mind the increasing needs of customers to have non-interest based transactions based on Islamic Laws several banks have started dual operations for banking under one roof, one for Islamic and another for conventional banking operations. Khan *et al*, (2008) have diagnosed and stated that the stability of financial segment is increased by Islamic banks. The concept of Islamic banking has been started since more than three decades and its concept is glowing (Maurer, 2001). The Islamic banking has been started with Dubai Islamic Bank since three decades ago which was opened up in 1975. It has discovered a considerable level of expansion and growth in the non-Muslim states as well such as North America and Europe. Khan and Bhatti (2008) have stated the Islamic Banking as the rapidly growing industries of this century in Middle East and Asia. Islamic Banking has achieved great level of satisfaction in the regions containing non-Muslims population (Siddiqi, 2008). This information of current satisfaction levels in banking sector and the determinants of satisfaction strongly suggests and directs to build upon major areas that show the way to extremely satisfied customers. Studies draw concentration, factors in branches; mainly personnel, convenience and branch locality are the mainly considerable components influencing customer satisfaction. In the world of banking in current situation and to stay competitive these factors are exceptionally significant for managers. In response to the current situation, several retail banks have very aggressively directing their strategies to increase satisfaction of customers and to create more and more loyalty through better

quality of services provided to their customers. Like other providers of services in the industry the banks have discovered that growing customer retention frequency can be having a considerable result on bank earnings. Rapidly growing expectations from bank customers have directed managers to be converted into focused on customers and to retain. For the objective to achieve better service quality, customer care initiatives have been introduced. A considerable connection found between the service quality determinants in Islamic banks stated and evaluated by (Qureshi *et al*, (2014). The names of determinants are 1-tangibles, 2-reliability, 3-responsiveness, 4-assurance and 5-empathy.

Financial institutions are situated to obtain the constructive results with having fundamentally customer base of satisfied customers. If their capability is enough to supply to the factors that enhance satisfaction in customers. Meeting customer's expectation would lead to satisfied customers and will be dependable on service provider and will suggest other people. Service quality is explained as appropriate technique that satisfy customer demands by fulfilling them with their required necessary services and products (Daniel & Berinyuy, 2010). Customer satisfaction directs to enhance loyalty of customers who absolutely assist in business enlargement and earnings.

Research background (Area of research)

Since several years, various studies have been conducted on Islamic banks having key focus on customers. Rapidly growing expectations from bank customers have directed managers to be converted into focused on customers and to retain. For the objective to achieve better service quality, customer care initiatives have been introduced. Consequences from various studies show that the expenditure of having a new customer is more costly and it is far better to retain existing customers (Reichheld & Sasser, 1990). Funding in service quality provided to customers lead to increased earnings and grasping the share of market (Rust & Zahorik, 1993). Satisfied customers may results in repeat purchase and expansion of market share in the industry. Customer satisfaction leads to profitability, customer loyal base

and increased earnings (Hallowell, 1996). Service quality is acknowledged by Parasuraman *et al*, (1994) as one of the fundamentals of customer satisfaction. Leonard and Spencer (1991) analyzed two perceptions of customers for ATMs. It is considered as important accomplishment and contribution to the banking industry is first perception. The second perception of customers is opposing and ATMs are not considered as important accomplishment and contribution to the banking industry. In Pakistan, the query arise that what are the fundamentals in Islamic banking thorough which customers are lead towards satisfaction or dissatisfaction. The information of current satisfaction levels in banking sector and the determinants of satisfaction strongly suggests and directs to build upon major areas that show the way to highly satisfied customers. Ribbink *et al*, (2004) have been stated that a boost in customer satisfaction can be resulted by the innovative developments in financial industries.

An earlier study cited from Levesque and McDougall (1996) assists and highlighted the design of non-satisfactory service to customers result in decline in non-willingness for recommending the service to other people or other person by word of mouth. This would direct to rise in switching by unsatisfied customers of the organizations. So, for any of the firm that is either market oriented or customer focused the influence of satisfaction & retention of customer cannot be taken too lightly in development of strategy (Kohli & Jaworski, 1990).

Laroche and Taylor (1988) identified the reason or the factors behind convenience and accessibility of a customer. If service provider is capable and delivers convenience and benefits by its accessibility on continuous basis to its customers will result in possibly bang customer satisfaction. Satisfaction of customers can be measured as the core of achievement in the world of today's highly competitive business situation in banking sector. It is more and more becoming a corporate goal and many of the organizations make every effort for quality in the services & products (Bitner & Hubbert, 1994).

In the framework of determinants of customer satisfaction various studies have been conducted containing of great importance to marketers of the industry. It is mandatory to make available the

complete series and the exact quality of services otherwise failure will certainly results in major difficulties in customer retention and acquiring new ones. Therefore, customer satisfaction and service quality have established huge consideration from marketers of service industry and researchers of academics (Spreng & Mackoy, 1996).

Problem Statement

The basis of operations conducting by Islamic Banking is on the basis of Shari'ah and Laws of Islam. Keeping in mind the increasing needs to have non-interest based transactions based on Islamic Laws several banks have started dual operations for banking under one roof, one for Islamic and another for conventional banking operations (Warde, 2000). The Islamic banking has been started with Dubai Islamic Bank since three decades ago which was opened up in 1975. It has discovered a considerable level of expansion and growth in North America and Europe. Islamic Banking is achieving great levels in the non-Muslim regions (Siddiqi, 2008). Importance of perceived quality is stated by Peeler (1996) that it is a key question in the banking sector. Since more than three decades Islamic banks are being operated alongside the non-Islamic banks. Like any other traditional banks, they do mobilize deposits and serve almost with same facilities but forms of operation of Islamic Banks is based on Islamic. There is no Law (Shari'ah) found in conventional or commercial banks and this is one of the big difference in both categories of the institutions worldwide. In this way Islamic and non-Islamic banking differs from each other in various ways. One of the foremost dissimilarity is the basis of transactions on spread rates and the condition of using certain financial instruments in operations of bank which is being carried out while transactions are executed.

Like other service providers Retail banks have revealed that growing customer retention rates can have a considerable impact on earnings. Rapidly growing expectations from bank customers have directed managers to be converted into focused on customers and to retain. In order to get better the quality of services provided, the customer care initiatives have been introduced. Service quality is

converted into a key question in banking now days (Stafford, 1994).

Qureshi *et al*, (2014) initiated that there is considerable connection found between the service quality determinants of Islamic banks. A theoretical gap has been observed that loyal customer base and market share of Islamic Banks can be enhanced by providing better quality of services to achieved customer satisfactions at optimum level.

Objectives of the study

Giving notice to the suggestions and understandings by earlier literatures conducted on this subject the mean of this study is to carry out a review of the set of different factors and determinants which are really capable of being included in this evaluation. Since several years, various studies have been conducted on Islamic banks having key focus on customers. Rapidly growing expectations from bank customers have directed managers to be converted into focused on customers and to retain.

Funding in service quality provided to customers lead to increased earnings and grasping the share of market (Rust & Zahorik, 1993). Satisfied customers may results in repeat purchase and expansion of market share in the industry. Customer satisfaction leads to profitability, customer loyal base and increased earnings (Hallowell, 1996). Service quality is acknowledged by Parasuraman *et al*, (1994) as one of the fundamentals of customer satisfaction.

The current research is having a focus on dimensions of customer service quality on customer satisfaction in the Islamic banking sector. Even though customers give very special concentration to the operations of Islamic banks and non-interest based transactions, but the way services are delivered matters to them too and cannot be ignored at any cost.

This research demonstrates that there is a considerable connection among the determinants of quality of services in Islamic banks and customer satisfaction. The names of determinants are 1-tangibles, 2-reliability, 3-responsiveness, 4-assurance, 5-empathy and 6-compliance.

Broad Objective

The research is the contribution for Islamic banking literature and managers of Islamic banks. It represents framework which shows connection between 6 determinants of service quality in the banking sector. This study cannot be applied to whole and it cannot be generalized, as it is conducted in Karachi that is one city of Pakistan. It may also be helpful to conduct it in whole Pakistan and make use of bigger the sample size. A theoretical gap has been observed that loyal customer base and market share of Islamic Banks can be enhanced by providing better quality of services to achieve customer satisfactions at optimum level.

Specific Objectives

- i. Compliance is used as a determinant of service quality to determine relationship between quality of services provided to customers and customer satisfaction.
- ii. Assurance is used as a determinant of service quality to determine relationship between quality of services provided to customers and customer satisfaction.
- iii. Reliability is used as a determinant of service quality to determine relationship between quality of services provided to customers and customer satisfaction is used as a determinant of service quality.
- iv. Tangibility is used as a determinant of service quality to determine relationship between quality of services provided to customers and customer satisfaction is used as a determinant of service quality.
- v. Empathy is used as a determinant of service quality to determine relationship between quality of services provided to customers and customer satisfaction is used as a determinant of service quality.
- vi. Responsiveness is used as a determinant of service quality to determine relationship between quality of services provided to customers and customer satisfaction is used as a determinant of service quality.

Significance of the Study

Since more than three decades Islamic banks are being operated alongside the non-Islamic banks. Like any other traditional banks, they do mobilize deposits and serve almost with same facilities but forms of operation of Islamic Banks is based on

Islamic. There is no Law (Shari'ah) found in conventional or commercial banks and this is one of the big difference in both categories of the institutions worldwide. In this way Islamic and non-Islamic banking deviates from each other in various ways. One of the foremost dissimilarity is the basis of transactions on spread rates and the condition of using certain financial instruments in operations of bank which is being carried out while transactions are executed. The study also characterize Islamic banking as those financial institutions which comply fully on Islamic Laws and rules, with non-interest based transactions and have very progressive and inspired financial engineering to provide and recommend very effective and aggressive financing services.

Scope of the study

The research is having a focus on factors of customer service quality in Islamic banks sector. It demonstrates that, even though customers give very special concentration to the operations of Islamic banks based on non-interest based transactions, but the way of delivery of services matters a lot to them and cannot be ignored at any cost.

Limitations of the Study

This study cannot be applied to whole and it cannot be generalized, as it is conducted in Karachi that is one city of Pakistan. It may also be helpful to conduct it in whole Pakistan and make use of bigger the sample size. A theoretical gap has been observed that loyal customer base and market share of Islamic Banks can be enhanced by providing better quality of services to achieve customer satisfactions at optimum level.

Summary

This research demonstrates that there is a considerable connection among the factors of service quality in Islamic banks and customer satisfaction. The names of factors are 1-tangibles, 2-reliability, 3-responsiveness, 4-assurance, 5-empathy and 6-compliance.

Literature Review

Introduction

In this chapter of this research various studies has been summarized in reference with current study that the growing customer retention rates can have a considerable impact on earnings. Rapidly growing expectations from bank customers have directed managers to be converted into focused on customers and to retain. The customer care initiatives have been introduced in order to obtain better service quality provided. Consequences from various studies show that the expenses of acquiring a new customer from market are more costly and expensive rather than retaining existing customers.

Theoretical Background

Janahi and Mubarak (2017) have examined the influence of service quality on customer satisfaction. They have recommended in the literature that customers of Islamic banks give exceptional concentration to the basis of operations of which is according to the laws of Islam while transactions are executed with Islamic banks but the importance of services delivered to the customers cannot be ignored. The paper presents a model which shows connection among six determinants of service quality. The survey instrument was validated by five experts before collection of samples for the purpose of validity and reliability. On the basis of results it is demonstrated that all the hypotheses used in this research are accepted statistically and proved that the customer service quality is having an important and helpful influence on the dependant variable which is customer satisfaction. This literature can influence with a critical plan of rising retention rate of customers and customer satisfaction. The study cannot be generalized as it is conducted in the Bahrain. It may be functional to make bigger the sample size.

Paul *et al*, (2016) have assessed the influence of very significant quality determinants of service on customer satisfaction. The similarity in public and private sector banks is also assessed in India. They have conducted an exploratory study. Primary data is used by using survey method and regression analysis is performed to identify negative and positive relationship of variable. There were total 500

respondents out of which 250 respondents from private sector and 250 respondents from public sector banks in India. Each respondent must be having at least one bank account. The difference is found in the mechanisms of public and private sector banks. The dependent variable was "overall satisfaction. It is concluded that there is a big room of improvement remaining in the quality of service provided by both private and public sector banks. Private Banks spend very heavily in personnel and tangibles of the bank to grant customers with a grand experience while on the other hand public sector banks does not spend heavily in personnel and tangibles of the bank. Customers have very specific and customized needs and they expect to be fulfilled by the Bank. Customer service should be a proactive exercise and officials of banks should take necessary initiatives for the betterment of customer satisfaction. For having a satisfying banking experience queries and problems of customers should be addressed and solutions should be communicated with immediate effects.

Ashraf (2014) have examined the influence of Islamic finance on satisfaction of customer and service quality provided. With reference to the fact that the major banks of world are fascinated in the course of action of Islamic banking because Muslims contribute a major segment in the entire world's population and it is a great game. Moreover this is descriptive research in nature and 250 respondents were participated in that project to investigate the self-governance for collection of facts. Data analysis has been checked by applying pilot testing on 50 results of respondents and then used for proper research and using data for main objective of the study via SPSS. Bankers can get assist from the literature to investigate the behavior of the customers and can apply techniques to retain of inject loyal customer base for their business growth. The sampling method used in this study is non-probabilistic and According to Zikmund (1997) the sampling of non-probability is very ease because in this method information can be collected from the associated sample or the unit of the study that are simply available. This sampling is used when a large number of data is needed in minimized cost with ease. Five points likert scale is used to calculate the

results in numbers. It has been concluded that attitudes of banks toward the bank Halal improve customer perception about the quality of the service and his / her satisfaction with Islamic banks based on the positive results. This is to confirm that workers are well prepared with the knowledge to manage clients and their functions. Further study is suggested on the current topic with people of different age groups, led by education and earnings on the same set to ensure the uniformity of the outcome by comparing the data with current outcomes. The number of respondents can also be increase the data accuracy in results for generalization of the study.

Fatima and Razzaue (2014) examined the impact of service quality on overall satisfaction of customers. AMOS is used for structural equation modeling and data analysis. 212 customers of bank were considered as respondents for validation of model. The study is having its limitations as it has been conducted on Bangladesh only and cannot be generalized. It is recommended in the literature that customers of Islamic banks give exceptional concentration to the basis of operations of which is according to the laws of Islam while transactions are executed with Islamic banks but the importance of services delivered to the customers cannot be ignored.

Qureshi *et al*, (2012) examined the determinants of expected service quality banks of Pakistan. A sample of 800 people was selected from several branches of Islamic and conventional banks from Khyber Pakhtoonkhawa a northern province of Pakistan. The questionnaire used in the literature was self designed for data collection. Likert scale consisting of five points is used in questionnaire collected from survey. It is recommended in the literature that customers of Islamic banks give exceptional concentration to the basis of operations of which is according to the laws of Islam while transactions are executed with Islamic banks but the importance of services delivered to the customers cannot be ignored. The result shows a considerable relation found among service quality and its determinants. Further research is suggested to be conducted by adding some more cities to this research to enhance the reliability of data and for generalization of results.

Rehman.A (2012) has investigated the connection among satisfaction & service quality in Islamic banks of Pakistan, United Arab Emirates and United Kingdom. The study used a sample of only 225 respondents; 75 from each state. Regression technique for analysis and Descriptive statistics has been used to make the assessment of data collected from 225 people. The results conclude that suitable reliability has been observed. Similarities are found in Pakistani and UK customers whereas results of customers of UAE showed a few dissimilarity. The result shows a considerable relation found among service quality and its determinants. It is recommended in that customers of Islamic banks give exceptional concentration to the basis of operations of which is according to the laws of Islam while transactions are executed with Islamic banks but the importance of services delivered to the customers cannot be ignored. Further research is suggested to be conducted by adding some more states to this research to enhance the reliability of data and for generalization of results.

Estiri.M *et al*, (2011), clarified and enhanced the concept and method to measure the determinants of expected service quality in banks of Iran. To measure customer satisfaction the grouping of different attributes into dimension of quality has been made. Survey technique was used via questionnaire to collect descriptive data about framework dimensions and then checked with reliability and validity to avoid any biasness. Factor analysis was implemented. It is concluded that the outcomes and implications of the present research is helpful. The research is also restricted to a single market but the result shows a considerable relation found among service quality and its determinants. Further research is suggested to be conducted by adding some more states to this research to enhance the reliability of data and for generalization of results.

Awan.H *et al*, (2011) have compared the connection of service quality & customer satisfaction. The functional extent of service quality is assessed by a modified scale 'SERVQUAL'. Moreover the research also has the impact of factors of service quality on the behavioral intentions of customers and customer satisfaction. Survey technique was to collect data for sample and questionnaire consisting SERVQUAL

scale was used. Data collected from 200 conveniently major banks. Factor analysis performed for assessment of data. The study is having useful meaning for policy makers of banks to understand the objective of their customers. It has been concluded after results that this study has managerial implications and can be used to detect gaps in performance of organizations. It is recommended in the literature that Customer satisfaction plays a catalyst role for any banks whether Islamic or Conventional to form consumer's future purchase intentions. Customer service is the managerial procedure which businesses need to adapt to attract business opportunities and enhance satisfaction level of customers.

Alhemoud (2010) evaluated customer satisfaction in bank services provided in Kuwait. By using a questionnaire consisting of 35 structured questionnaires. 605 samples were taken into consideration and used out of 700. The processes of distributing questionnaires were executed randomly. To make the data error free validity was checked and then reliability test was conducted. Findings revealed that in Kuwait, independent variable has very significant impact on dependant variable. Bank managers of the state can avail multiple benefits by using this literature to create a competitive edge by enhancing customer satisfaction. The research suffers from lack of generalization due to minimized cost and time constraints. It is recommended in the literature that Customer satisfaction plays a catalyst role for any banks to form consumer's future purchase intentions. Customer service is the managerial procedure which businesses need to adapt to attract business opportunities and enhance revenue of the business.

Lundhal.N *et al*, (2009) have assessed the relationship of technical & functional dimensions of service quality in banks. A random sampling was done in various companies of Sweden to collect data and 331 employees were chosen for filing questionnaire and 221 were taken into consideration after reduction of data rejected by SPSS. The technique used for the analysis was Regression analysis on data collected. The functional dimensions of service quality showed correlation in results with customer satisfaction. It is revealed that

the bank relationships does not only depends on the efficiencies of banks services but also depends on the care which is delivered to customer my bank personnel. Results conclude that personal interaction plays a catalyst role in enhancing customer satisfaction. Banks should focus on training of personnel rather than solely on products. However the results are positive but more and more study is suggested and number of sample should be increase to enhance the accuracy of results and for generalization of studies.

Amin.M and Isa.Z (2008) have observed an association by using SEM approach between perception of quality and satisfaction in Malaysian Islamic banking. SERVQUAL scale is composed of six difference determinants; the names of determinants are 1-tangibles, 2-reliability, 3-responsiveness, 4-assurance, 5-empathy and 6-compliance to measure service quality. The result suggests that the relationship between two variables is significant. More and more research is suggested in order to get precise outlay on the subject research. It is recommended in the literature that Customer satisfaction plays a catalyst role for any Bank to form customer intentions. The study is limited and restricted from lack of generalization so the number of banks involved in the research study should be increase as well as the number of respondents.

Maddern.H *et al.*,(2007) evaluated the determinants of customer satisfaction, particularly exploring its influence on service quality of management of business processes. The research is supported by a large UK financial services company which was participated. Customer Satisfaction is a serious business requirement. It is recommended in the literature that Customer satisfaction plays a catalyst role for any service provider to form consumer's future purchase intentions. Customer service is the managerial procedure which businesses needs to adapt to attract business opportunities, enhance revenue of the business, make more and more reliable access of the market and enhance satisfaction level of customers.

Arasli.H *et al.*, (2005) have examined the perceptions of service quality in Greek Cypriot bank customers'. In this study, the questionnaire used is mainly composed of three parts containing 22 total items. A

huge difficulty is faced while conducting reviews and that has restricted the potential sample size which is 260 only. Results from literature explain that predictor variables are having significant impact on dependant variable. It is suggested to conduct more research by using more accurate data and sample size should be increased to generalize the research.

Jamal and Naser (2003) have identified the key components that contribute to the retail banking. First Women Bank Ltd was chosen for the study and a questionnaire was designed. The process resulted in a sample of 165 fulfilled questionnaires and the 55% were useable out of 100% and total questionnaires were 300 distributed randomly. The questionnaire contained a part on profile of customer along with various demographics information. It is recommended in the literature that Customer satisfaction plays a catalyst role to find consumer's future purchase intentions. Customer service is the managerial procedure which businesses needs to adapt to attract business opportunities, enhance revenue of the business, and enhance satisfaction level of customers. It is recommended in the literature that customers of banks give exceptional concentration to the convenience, rate of returns, tangibles but the importance of services delivered to the customers cannot be ignored.

Owen and Othman (2001) have conducted study in Kuwait for the importance of Islamic banking. A framework consists of 34 items named CARTER model is used for assessment. This study shows significance of contents of carter model and a very strong causal connection between variables in Islamic banking. Since more than three decades Islamic banks are being operated alongside the non-Islamic banks. Like any other traditional banks, they do mobilize deposits and serve almost with same facilities but forms of operation of Islamic Banks is based on Islamic. There is no Law (Shari'ah) found in conventional or commercial banks and this is one of the big difference in both categories of the institutions worldwide. In this way Islamic and non-Islamic banking differs from each other. One of the foremost dissimilarity is the basis of transactions on spread rates and the condition of using certain financial instruments in operations of bank which is being carried out while transactions are executed.

SERVQUAL model based on five dimensions has been used by them. The survey was conducted in Kuwait KFH the second largest retail bank of Kuwait. The customers of the KFH bank were used respondents. By applying regression analysis on questionnaires collected from bank customers based on likert scale the study reveals that customers of Islamic banks give exceptional concentration to the basis of operations of which is according to the laws of Islam while transactions are executed with Islamic banks but the importance of services delivered to the customers cannot be ignored.

Jahanshahi (2011) states that Customer service is the organizational process which organizations take up to growing competition, attraction of business opportunities, increase earnings, make more better market access and increase level of customer satisfaction. It also establishes a positive relationship between high levels of service quality and financial performance.

An earlier study cited from Levesque and McDougall (1996) assists and highlighted the design of non-satisfactory service to customers result in decline in non-willingness for recommending the service to other people or other person by word of mouth. This would direct to rise in switching by unsatisfied customers of the organizations. So, for any of the firm that is either market oriented or customer focused the influence of satisfaction & retention of customer cannot be taken too lightly in development of strategy (Kohli & Jaworski, 1990).

Since several years, various studies have been conducted on Islamic banks having key focus on customers. Rapidly growing expectations from bank customers have directed managers to be converted into focused on customers and to retain. For the objective to achieve better service quality, customer care initiatives have been introduced. Consequences from various studies show that the expenditure of having a new customer is more costly and it is far better to retain existing customers (Reichheld & Sasser, 1990).

Kristensen et al, (2001) optimized an association among customer satisfaction and loyalty. The model creates linked between customer satisfaction and its determinants. It is recommended in the literature that Customer satisfaction plays a catalyst role for

any service provider to form consumer's future purchase intentions. Customer service is the managerial procedure which businesses needs to adapt to attract business opportunities, enhance revenue of the business, make more and more reliable access of the market and enhance satisfaction level of customers.

Laroche and Taylor (1988) identified the reason or the factors behind convenience and accessibility of a customer. If service provider is capable and delivers convenience and benefits by its accessibility on continuous basis to its customers will result in possibly bang customer satisfaction. Satisfaction of customers can be measured as the core of achievement in the world of today's highly competitive business situation in banking sector. It is more and more becoming a corporate goal and many of the organizations make every effort for quality in the services & products (Bitner & Hubbert, 1994).

Leonard and Spencer (1991) analyzed two perceptions of customers for ATMs. It is considered as important accomplishment and contribution to the banking industry is first perception. The second perception of customers is opposing and ATMs are not considered as important accomplishment and contribution to the banking industry. In Pakistan, the query arise that what are the fundamentals in Islamic banking through which customers are lead towards satisfaction or dissatisfaction. The information of current satisfaction levels in banking sector and the determinants of satisfaction strongly suggests and directs to build upon major areas that show the way to highly satisfied customers. Ribbink *et al*, (2004) have been stated that a boost in customer satisfaction can be resulted by the innovative developments in financial industries.

Sowailim (2013) Islamic & non-Islamic banking effort together to accomplish bank needs of customers and the core segregation between them is their basis of operations. The basis of operations conducting by Islamic Banking is on (Sharia'h) and Islamic laws. Keeping in mind the increasing needs to have non-interest based transactions based on Islamic Laws several banks have started dual operations for banking under one roof, one for Islamic and another for conventional banking operations. The stability of financial sector is

increased by Islamic banks. The concept of Islamic banking has been started since more than three decades and its concept is glowing.

Identification of Researchable gaps

Islamic banks are focusing their customers by using their form of operations which is Sharia’h laws (compliance) in their transaction with a critical aim of rising customer base of loyal customers but they should also keeping an eye on the service quality they are providing to their customers as it matters a lot to them. Although customers pay very special concentration to their operations based on Islamic rules and laws and non-interest based in their transactions, but how the services are delivered really matters to them too and cannot be ignored at any cost.

Hypothesis

- H1. Compliance has a constructive impact on customer satisfaction in Islamic banking.
- H2. Assurance has a constructive impact on customer satisfaction in Islamic banking.
- H3. Reliability has a constructive impact on customer satisfaction in Islamic banking.
- H4. Tangibility has a constructive impact on customer satisfaction in Islamic banking.
- H5. Empathy has a constructive impact on customer satisfaction in Islamic banking.
- H6. Responsiveness has a constructive impact on customer satisfaction in Islamic banking.

Hypothesis development / Proposed Research Framework

Conceptual framework

Summary

Islamic banks have focused on their customers by using their form of operations which is based on Islamic rules and Laws in transactions. Although customers pay very special concentration to their

operations but the importance of services delivered to the customers cannot be ignored at any cost.

Research Methodology

Introduction

Various studies have been summarized in this chapter in reference with current study that the banking services are getting more challenging. Rapidly growing expectations from bank customers have directed managers to be converted into focused on customers and to retain. For the objective to achieve better service quality, customer care initiatives have been introduced. Consequences from various literatures show that the expenses and cost of acquiring new customers are more costly rather than retaining existing customers. Various researches on bank marketing have been done having a focus on service provided to customers of Islamic banks over the years.

Research Approach

This study represents a framework which is used in Islamic banking literatures shows a causal relationship between service quality & customer satisfaction. Consumers of four major Islamic banks are taken into involvement in this research.

Research Purpose

Since four decades Islamic banks are being operated alongside the non-Islamic banks. Just like any other conventional banks, they do organize deposits and serve almost with same facilities but forms of operation of Islamic Banks is based on Islamic. There is no Law (Shari'ah) found in conventional or commercial banks and this is one of the big difference in both categories of the institutions worldwide. In this way Islamic & conventional banking varies from one another in various ways. One of the foremost dissimilarity is the basis of transactions on spread rates and the condition of using certain financial instruments in operations of bank which is being carried out while transactions are executed. The studies also characterize Islamic banking as an institution which complies entirely on Islamic rules & Laws, with non-interest based transactions and have very effective and aggressive financing services.

Data Source

The structured questionnaire for research is used and given to 400 targeted customers and selected from the branches of Islamic banks in Karachi. Questionnaires were filled with due care that no questionnaire should go for rejection due to incomplete form filled by customer. As a result 100 percent questionnaires are taken into consideration as not a single is rejected.

Target Population

The Target population of this research is those people who are living in Karachi and have customer relationship with Islamic banks and have perception and expectation of perceived quality services.

Sample Size

Four hundred people are selected at random from branches of Islamic Banks and the selected customers are those who have visited branches or their representatives found in branches.

Data Collection Technique/Tools

This research focuses on finding the connection between the qualities of services delivered to customers in Islamic Banks of Pakistan. The framework and questionnaire is used in several researches and it is validated. To obtain a broader reaction the sample data was collected from major Islamic banks that are operating in Pakistan and have branches in Karachi and a convenient sample of 400 customers selected at random.

Statistical Technique/ Tools

In this study Questionnaire technique is used for data collection from the customers of banks. Simple regression method is used to identify the connection and all hypotheses. Before applying regression analysis a pilot testing on 50 questionnaires has been applied to validate the data. Instrument was mainly consisting two parts. The initial part containing personal details of respondents such as demographics of the respondent, age, education and income of the respondents. The second part consist of mainly six sections that were determinants of the service quality adopted from earlier research and then sub divided into more categories according to the features of determinants. Then factor analysis and regression

analysis is performed to extract the conclusion from the collected data.

Summary

This section summarizes the Methodology of research, purpose, data collection source, Target population, sample size, technique of data collection and statistical tools used in this research to identify the relationship between variables.

Data Analysis

Introduction

This paper has been having a focus to calculate and compute the influence of the service quality

determinants on customer satisfaction. Survey instrument has already been used in several researches and it is validated. To obtain a broader reaction, the study was executed on four Islamic banks operating in Pakistan and has branches in Karachi. 400 customers were randomly selected for a convenient sample because of time and cost constraints. The instrument used for data collection and assessment is structured and adopted from earlier research of Owen & Othman, 2001.

Tables and Analysis

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.973	.974	30

Table showing the reliability evaluation of variables used in this study. This analysis is generally used for ensuring the consistency of the collected data internally. The above appended figure shows that all the factors of service quality are reliable as it is > 0.9.

Nunnally and Bernstein (1994) stated the minimum standard of Cronbach's a value should be greater than 0.70. Therefore with reference to the citation results are indicating the fine internal uniformity in the data.

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.890
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	13179.992
	df	231
	Sig.	.000

Table shows the relationship between dependant and independent variables. Above result show KMO value 0.89 which is nearest to 1 and very far from 0. Normally, the value lies between '0 < KMO < 1' and

If KMO > 0.5, the sample is adequate. Here, KMO = 0.890 which indicates that the sample is adequate and we may proceed with the Factor Analysis.

Pattern Matrix^a

Component	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
T1		0.999					
T3		0.999					
R3	0.99						

R4	0.99						
RS1				0.976			
RS4				0.888			
A2						0.965	
A3						0.965	
E3		0.978					
E4		0.978					
C2			0.916				
C4			0.979				
CS1					0.969		
CS4					0.969		

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
 Rotation Method: Promax with Kaiser Normalization.

Table shows the result of pattern matrix and seven groups are formed for seven different variables including dependant and independent variables.

After successful formation of all groups the data is convergent and valid for performing factor analysis.

Component Correlation Matrix

Component	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	1						
2	0.147	1					
3	0.442	0.353	1				
4	0.448	0.329	0.593	1			
5	0.591	0.244	0.519	0.449	1		
6	0.471	0.292	0.651	0.646	0.574	1	
7	0.547	0.294	0.645	0.561	0.653	0.698	1

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
 Rotation Method: Promax with Kaiser Normalization.

Table shows the result of component correlation matrix.

Regression Analysis

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.890 ^a	0.793	0.789		0.23757

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.363	0.117		3.091	0.002
	Tangible	0.401	0.028	0.399	14.521	0
	Reliability	-0.051	0.057	-0.051	-0.895	0.371
	Responsiveness	0.223	0.043	0.255	5.175	0

Assurance	0.351	0.048	0.375	7.305	0
Empathy	-0.269	0.052	-0.274	-5.155	0
Compliance	0.327	0.042	0.366	7.795	0

Table shows the result of regression analysis performed via SPSS and customer satisfaction placed as dependant variable and service quality determinants are placed is independent variables. The results are indicating that hypotheses are being accepted for tangibles, assurance, empathy, compliance and responsiveness are considerable &

are associated with customer satisfaction because the value of sig in above appended table is less than 0.05. Hence hypothesis for reliability is rejected because (sig. , 0.37). F-statistics conclude that the overall framework is strongly significant and superior fit. Below is the equation of the model derived from this study.

$$\text{Customer Satisfaction} = 0.363\text{Constant} + \text{Tang}(0.401) + \text{Rel}(-0.051) + \text{Resp}(0.223) + \text{Assur} (0.351) + \text{Emp} (-0.269) + \text{Comp} (0.327)$$

Hypothesis	Results
H1. Compliance has a constructive impact on customer satisfaction in Islamic banking	Accepted
H2. Assurance has a constructive impact on customer satisfaction in Islamic banking	Accepted
H3. Reliability has a constructive impact on customer satisfaction in Islamic banking	Rejected
H4. Tangibility has a constructive impact on customer satisfaction in Islamic banking	Accepted
H5. Empathy has a constructive impact on customer satisfaction in Islamic banking	Accepted
H6. Responsiveness has a constructive impact on customer satisfaction in Islamic banking	Accepted

Summary

This section concludes the results of techniques applied on the collected data from survey. It is revealed that out of six hypotheses one is rejected and five are accepted. Overall model is shows significance relationship between dependant and independent variables.

services delivered to the customers cannot be ignored.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Introduction

This study shows causal relationship of service quality determinants & satisfaction of customers of Islamic Banking. Increase in service quality level will provide increased customer satisfaction results in loyal customer base and probable chances to get more customers by word of mouth marketing of satisfied customers. Building strategic connections to keep in contact with consumers is an additional point. Customers of Islamic banks give exceptional concentration to the basis of operations of which is according to the laws of Islam while transactions are executed with Islamic banks but the importance of

Theoretical Contribution

The aim of the current study is to put an addition to the literature of Islamic banking by investigating the strength of various determinants of independent variable on customer satisfaction. It is suggested to conduct more and more research by increasing sample size or by adding some more cities to generalize the study on the whole country. It is also an option for future research to make a comparative analysis of Islamic and non Islamic banks on the basis of service quality.

Managerial Implications

It is the responsibility of a manager of the Islamic Bank that to consider first responder’s financial position rather than its emotional or spiritual state. Although the quality of service has an impact on customer satisfaction, and it cannot guarantee customer loyalty in the banking sector. This study cannot be applied to whole and it cannot be

generalized, as it is conducted in Karachi that is one city of Pakistan. It may also be helpful to conduct it in whole Pakistan and make use of bigger the sample size. It can also be helpful to involve comparative analysis of Islamic and non Islamic banking with regard to customer service quality and customer satisfaction. It is suggested that loyal customer base and market share of Islamic Banks can be enhanced by providing better quality of services to achieve customer satisfactions at optimum level.

Summary

To succeed in an aggressive environment, managers must be very well trained and have awareness of unusual aspects of services quality requirement by customers. The rapidly changing industry dynamics of banking in current scenario, a competitive target to score much in gaining market share of customers and target of increased rate of retention the identification of different customer needs & demands by Islamic banks is required on war footing basis. After identification the hard work to accomplish such necessities is also required. This study recommends managers and policy makers of Islamic banks should go out of the box and various skills such as communication skills and interpersonal skills are need to be implemented to ensure more and more improved customer satisfaction level. Managers of Islamic banks are recommended to think laterally about several of dimensions of service quality mentioned in this study that positively affect customer satisfaction and meet expectations of customers.

Conclusion

The results revealed that five hypotheses are accepted and one is rejected out of total six hypotheses and it is proven statistically that the framework model used in this study is considerable and its implication is very important for the industry. It is concluded that Customer satisfaction plays a catalyst role for any service provider to form consumer's future purchase intentions. Customer service is managerial procedure and required by all businesses. All factors operationalised in this research and the significance of implementation of service quality determinants is proved to reach at an excellent level of customer

satisfaction within the context of Islamic banking transactions.

The result of this research are likewise with the recent study conducted by Janahi and Mubarak (2017) which indicates that the positive and strong relationship of customer perceptions and satisfaction. Overall, this study confirms the considerable and positive relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction in Islamic banking.

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